

Enhancing Reliability in 6G Networks Based on User-Driven AI

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Abstract—In the sixth-generation (6G) era of mobile networks, services will be centered around users, following a user-centric approach. Inspired by the fifth-generation (5G) network paradigms, this redesigned architecture will be driven by the openness of the 6G system and the distributed edge-cloud continuum. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) integration to the network brings the latest emerging advancements in the field. Mission-critical applications, such as remote surgery, metaverse, and autonomous vehicles, expect high Quality of Experience (QoE) which can only be ensured through strong network and service reliability. In this paper, we propose a novel framework for ensuring user-centric reliability on 6G networks, based on AI algorithms, that extends over the whole 6G edge-cloud continuum infrastructure. In particular, we present two profiling methods (service and security) that are able to identify and act proactively against malicious activities and infrastructure-related issues using AI, taking into account the unique user characteristics. We also perform an evaluation analysis aiming to designate the need and the invaluable use of the user-centric characteristics, e.g., user position, speed, etc., when trying to optimize the QoE and ensure reliability.

Keywords—6G, reliable communications, user-centricity, edge-cloud continuum, artificial intelligence, quality of experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of sixth-generation (6G) networks, the integration of a wide range of technologies and applications, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), heralds a significant advancement in order to offer fresh categories of services and applications to the end users [1]–[7]. Users expect a high Quality of Experience (QoE) without interruptions, which can only be ensured through high network and service reliability. The reliability of the whole life cycle of a service in 6G networks requires the satisfaction of a number of indicators, not only related to performance, like availability, low latency and consistency, but also to security. According to the requirements and capabilities of IMT-2030 [2], reliability over the air interface could range between 10^{-5} and 10^{-7} or even 10^{-9} for industrial applications. In the context of critical applications, such as autonomous vehicles, remote surgery, critical infrastructures and smart cities, any failure in

satisfying service reliability, including security breaches, could lead to disastrous consequences [5].

The current network architecture's limitations are inherent in the traditional operator-centric strategies. These strategies have resulted in monolithic network entities like Mobility Management Entities (MMEs) and User Plane Functions (UPFs) in the fourth-generation (4G) and fifth-generation (5G) of mobile networks, respectively. This centralized architecture can become a bottleneck as the number of connected devices increases. To overcome these limitations, 6G aims to shift towards a user-centric architecture that enables user definition, configuration, and control, transforming the way that user interacts with network services and applications [8]. This user-centric approach requires personalized and adaptive services that respond dynamically to individual user needs and contexts. This level of personalization relies on the continuous stability, scalability and security of the whole network architecture to gather and process user data in real-time in a safe and secure manner. The user-centric 6G architecture will promote the deployment of network functions independently of location, facilitated by the openness and adaptability of the 5G system [9]. Inspired by the 5G core's openness and standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), this flexibility allows for the creation, scaling, and migration of services across the whole edge-cloud continuum.

Machine Learning (ML) and specifically Federated Learning (FL) and Reinforcement Learning (RL) can play a pivotal role in this vision, providing the so wanted level of security, confidentiality and consistency to the end-user [10]. Transforming the network structure from centralized to decentralized, ML can optimize the management of the resources on the continuum, network and user lever and provide reliable solutions for future distributed, intelligent and secure 6G edge-cloud network architectures [11], [12].

In this paper, we propose a comprehensive research approach aimed at designing, developing and validating a user-centric reliability framework, on top of the open, heterogeneous and distributed 6G core, across the edge-cloud continuum. This framework will examine the threats that can affect an application's reliability based on AI algorithms,

providing a holistic, secure, and reliable proposition for 6G applications. The focus will not be only on security but also on abnormalities in the 5G core and edge-cloud continuum infrastructure that can affect the Quality of Service (QoS). The candidate mechanism will be able to identify both known and zero-day attacks, as well as architecture anomalies, and it will adaptively respond in real-time according to user needs. Various methods and algorithms, including AI/ML techniques will be investigated in order to design the reliability approach with scope to optimize the Level of Trustworthiness (LoTw) [13], a crucial Key Value Indicator (KVI) for 6G. This KVI describes the guaranteed level of protection against certain attacks and threats. The LoTw, being more stringent due to the pervasive utility of 6G and burgeoning risk level, is tailored to the trustworthiness related requirements and data governance policies specified by each user, tenant, or human role.

The proposed user-centric reliability will be based on (a) *service* profiling and (b) *security* profiling to ensure the overall reliability of the application. The service profiling will help to identify how the user's characteristics are affecting the performance of the 6G edge-cloud continuum infrastructure, while the security profiling will focus more on security issues and abnormalities. The main goal of both profiling methods will be to aid in acting proactively via various actions, such as migrations, scaling, and resource allocation to optimize the QoE and maintain the overall 6G system reliability.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the works related to reliability in 6G, highlighting the gaps our research aims to fill. In Section III we present in detail the proposed novel approach for a user-centric reliability on 6G networks, including the data collection techniques and profiling methods. Next, Section IV provides an evaluation analysis aiming to confirm the need for user-related characteristics when trying to optimize the QoE metrics. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings and Section VI proposes future directions.

II. RELATED WORKS

The reliability of 6G wireless systems has become the center of attention for a large number of journal and conference publications due to the increasing demand for Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) to support mission-critical applications. The vision and the key requirements for 6G systems are described in [1]-[9], where the need for this type of communication is emphasized. The authors of these works discuss the challenges in achieving these goals and provide insights into various technological advancements, such as AI/ML tools, that can contribute to the design of reliable 6G networks.

The current section reviews the key contributions in the field and positions our research within this context. The vision for a new user-centric approach is relatively new to the research community, which has recently begun to explore its verification. The EU funds projects for the implementation of this 6G ecosystem, including "A Smart and Adaptive Framework for Enhancing Trust in 6G Networks" (SAFE-6G). SAFE-6G [13] is a HORIZON-JU-SNS funded research project which integrates a native trustworthiness framework within the open and distributed User Service Node (USN) / Network Service Node (NSN)-based 6G core by utilizing

(X)AI/ML techniques to manage user-centric safety, security, privacy, resilience, and reliability functions.

Only a few research works have been published related to this approach, including the [9], [14]-[19] where the shift from network function-focus to user-focus is analyzed. Specifically, in [9] an AI-native user centric network (UCN) architecture is proposed to be integrated into the 6G, which exploits ML algorithms to optimize network resource allocation and management of user services. Next, the authors in [14] discuss future developments in native AI within the User-Centric Access Network (UCAN) architecture, which can flexibly perform network tasks, such as control plane signaling, path selection, serving access point organization, and radio resource coordination. Further, in [15]-[17] researchers propose some changes that should be made to the current management and orchestration of the network to transition to the user-centric approach while in, [18], [19] the authors present the contribution of AI technology, such as FL within various components of the 6G network, towards a trusted, intelligent, zero-touch, service management.

Most existing studies mainly focus on the core network or specific segments, such as edge or cloud, without considering the whole continuum and specific user characteristics. Therefore, a comprehensive examination that integrates the entire 5G core and edge-cloud continuum, considering a user-centric reliability approach, remains underexplored. This gap highlights the main contribution of our work, that tries to address this need by proposing a novel framework that leverages AI to ensure user-centric service reliability across the entire 6G ecosystem. In the next section, we describe this framework in detail, outlining its architecture and the key innovations that distinguish it from existing approaches.

III. USER - CENTRIC RELIABILITY

The proposed innovative approach for a user-centric reliability on 6G networks, according to our vision, is based on *service* profiling and *security* profiling. Service profiling is more related to identifying how the user and his/her characteristics are affecting the performance metrics of the edge-cloud continuum infrastructure, such as CPU, memory, network bandwidth, and latency, in order to optimize the QoE via scaling, resource allocation, and migration actions. Security profiling is more related to identifying how the user is affecting the security of the infrastructure by performing extensive inspections for security threats and other abnormalities in order to act proactively in maintaining the overall 6G system reliability.

A. Data Monitoring - Collection

For both profiling methods, data will be collected from all different layers of the infrastructure. This multi-layer data collection is realized by monitoring and collecting data from the monitoring probes of all possible layers, including the edge-cloud continuum, the 5G core system, and the application/service plane. This includes data from all virtual computational and network resources, such as hardware devices, physical equipment, hypervisors, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, Software Defined Networking (SDN) controllers, virtual resources (Virtual Machines - VMs, Virtual Network Functions - VNFs, containers) and applications. Data collection is performed for different user workload parameters like number of concurrent requests, traffic per user, etc. Due to the heterogeneity and sensitivity

of the data across the edge-cloud continuum, we propose the deployment of an FL mechanism to enable a distributed training approach. This mechanism will leverage the full advantages offered by ML methods, while it will preserve data privacy, ownership and security by decentralizing data to the end-devices.

B. Service Profiling

The main novel component of the service profiling approach is the local model training module that incorporates various methods and algorithms, including AI/ML tools. The different algorithms of the module will be trained and optimized by the data collected through the multi-layer monitoring part. As depicted in Fig.1, the service will be profiled under different users and operational conditions, which are the input data, in order to identify their impact on the performance metrics (predicted outputs), which are the output data. Input data can be any user and service specific workload characteristic, such as the number of requests and traffic load per request, while output data can be metrics of every infrastructure layer, from physical to application, such as CPU load, memory footprint, and network bandwidth. After the profiling, the collected pairs of input and output data will be utilized to train several employed algorithms and models on each client side, which will be able to perform predictions on the target performance metrics and detect any possible “breaking point” on the infrastructure level.

Fig. 1. High level diagram of service profiling.

The local model training module's vision, shown in the middle of Fig.1, is to contain many algorithms, each with different complexity, starting from simple rule expressions and reaching complex Deep Learning (DL) models and RL. Given the computational resources and power consumption constraints of each IoT/edge device, it will try to deploy the appropriate algorithm to maximize the prediction accuracy. Furthermore, targeting a high estimation accuracy, it will utilize continuous training and data augmentation techniques in order to increase the size of the dataset when needed or to make it more balanced. At the run-time phase of the service profiling, all the accumulated intelligence will be used to make optimal decisions and configuration changes in the whole 6G edge-cloud continuum infrastructure, such as resource allocation, migration and scaling, as per user's requests and needs.

C. Security Profiling

During the security profiling phase, the service will be profiled initially under different types of attacks, e.g. DDoS attacks, botnet attacks, intrusion, etc. and then under normal conditions. As depicted in Fig.2, the proposed security profiling framework, like the service profiling, will be trained and optimized by the data collected through multi-layer monitoring under different user operational conditions. Various service configurations and traffic loads will be examined to ensure reliability, considering metrics such as CPU load, memory footprint, network bandwidth and service latency. It is also important to include in this profiling method security associated metrics, like packet headers, packet content, used protocol and request details. AI/ML algorithms will be trained and optimized by these datasets, and they will be deployed to detect these types of attacks during run-time.

Fig. 2. High level diagram of security profiling training.

In Fig.3, the end phase of the security profiling operation is depicted, where the service will be deployed in case it has successfully passed the attack tests. During run-time, the pre-trained AI/ML methods will aid in performing an extensive inspection for security threats as well as in observing the user's and service's impact on the various components of the infrastructure. This intelligence will help to identify not only security issues but also abnormalities in the whole 6G edge-cloud ecosystem that can affect the QoE. Like service profiling, security profiling will also act proactively via configuration changes on the appropriate layers of the infrastructure and network layer in order to maintain the overall 6G system reliability.

Fig. 3. High level diagram of security profiling at run-time.

In the next section, an evaluation-correlation analysis is presented, where a use case with an open access dataset is exploited based on the provided QoE metrics. The aim is to verify that the unique characteristics of each user can modify the QoE metrics and therefore can affect the overall system reliability.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Evaluation routine

As we already mentioned, the novel framework approach for user-centric reliability on 6G networks will examine threats and infrastructure-related issues that can affect service reliability based on AI/ML algorithms. These algorithms will be trained by datasets derived from the proposed multi-layer monitoring component that collects data from all related planes of the core network and edge-cloud continuum. Various methods based on RL/FL will be investigated for different datasets, collected from different administrative domains in the continuum, tailored to the purpose of each use case, preserving data privacy and security. The performance metrics related to these ML algorithms, such as training and inference times, accuracy of estimations, energy consumption, etc., along with the multi-layer monitoring data, will be stored to provide an evaluation report on the overall performance of the user-centric reliability framework.

B. Openly accessible datasets

A number of datasets that can be used to train ML methods to ensure reliability in 5G/6G networks has been published in open-access repositories [20]-[25]. In [20],[21] the authors collected a dataset that relates key performance metrics in 5G, such as the packet loss rate and packet delay, with the application type and category as well as with the slice type in order to train ML algorithms to predict the best network slice, even when the network fails. Next, in [22] a large dataset has been collected using a commercial 4G and 5G network where YouTube is the target application and QoE related metrics were gathered and associated with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Further, in [23], a dataset was generated exploiting real commercial cellular network traffic anonymized traces, injected over an emulated 5G platform that incorporated emulated radio access and 5G core network with the purpose of performing data analysis regarding novel network automation architectures, protocols and algorithms. Next, the authors in [24], published a dataset created using Simu5G, which is an open-source model library for the OMNeT++ simulation framework. This dataset includes data collected from 15 User Equipments (UEs) in 24 sessions, each of a 120-second simulation interval. The dataset includes 14 metrics and it is very useful that user-unique metrics are included, such as position and velocity, since they are directly affecting the QoS-related metrics, e.g. Channel Quality Indicator (CQI), Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), end to end delay, etc. These QoS metrics, in turn, affect the QoE experienced by the user, e.g., via the percentage of video frames arrived at the time of their display. Another dataset that relates the performance metrics, e.g. the CPU usage with the traffic details, like the number of active UEs, the gNB's downlink bit rate and the outbound traffic for a 5G video streaming use case is published in [25]. This dataset does not include user-related metrics, however it

can be effectively exploited to train ML methods to predict the relationship between the traffic details and the performance metrics. The same approach was followed in [26]-[27], where the need for collecting data from all possible layers of the architecture (application layer, virtual layer, physical layer) in order to not only ensure reliability but also to optimize the utilization of available resources was highlighted for two applications: Hadoop and a back-end service.

C. Impact of user characteristics

In this sub-section, we exploit the dataset presented in [24] to showcase the need to include the users' unique characteristics, e.g., position, speed, distance from the base station, type and capabilities of the device, etc., as input attributes to the ML algorithms that predict the QoE-related metrics, e.g., number of frames, latency, service time, etc. More specifically, we are based on the fact that the user details, like position and speed, strongly impact the QoS metrics, like end-to-end delay, CQI, SNIR, etc. For example, the longer the distance between the user and the base station is, the higher the attenuation is and, as a consequence, the lower the SINR. We show that these QoS metrics have a strong impact on QoE metrics, e.g. on the percentage of video frames arrived at the time of their display and in order to satisfy the user application reliability, all the user unique metrics need to be taken into account.

To estimate the correlation between the QoS and the QoE related metrics, we selected the Pearson correlation coefficient. In particular, we calculated the correlation between the frame percentage arrived at the time of its display, designated as “frames displayed” and the performance-related metrics, which are the

- i) CQI values, designated as “averageCqiDI”,
- ii) SINR value measured at packet reception, designated as “rcvdSinrDI”,
- iii) interarrival time between two Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP) packets, designated as “interArrivalTimeRtp”,
- iv) time between transmission and reception of an RTP packet, designated as “end2EndDelay”,

The Pearson correlation requires the same number of data over a time interval for both metrics of the selected pair of metrics. However, in the dataset of [24], the different attributes were neither collected at the same time nor with the same sampling rate. For this reason, we adopted the following procedure. We first selected the four pairs of “frames displayed” with the (i)-(iv) metrics presented above. Next, for each pair, we merged the two pairs of timestamp/metrics into a common timestamp that included all the timestamp values from both initial pairs of timestamp/metrics. Then, the (large) number of NaN values created in the non-common times were filled in using the propagation of the next valid observation (forward filling). Afterwards, the size of both metrics was similar and we estimated the Pearson correlation coefficient using the following expression

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - m_x)(y_i - m_y)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - m_x)^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - m_y)^2}} \quad (1)$$

where x_i and y_i denote the value of the i^{th} sample of x and y metrics and m_x and m_y , their average value, respectively. The parameter N represents the sample size. Next, the same procedure was followed for all 24 sessions and the obtained values were averaged to get a single value for each pair of metrics for each UE. The Pearson correlation coefficient for all 15 UEs is illustrated in Fig.4 for the four pairs of metrics. The first observation from this figure is a strong correlation between the four metrics and the user application metric. More specifically, a positive correlation is observed between the frames displayed and the averageCqiDl and rcvdSinrDl, while a negative correlation is computed between the frames displayed and the interArrivalTimeRtp and end2EndDelay. This is expected, as the higher signal quality can lead to a higher frame percentage arriving at the time of its display, while a larger end-to-end delay or a higher inter-arrival time impact negatively the frame percentage arriving at the time of its display. Moreover, we can observe that for the majority of the UEs (except for a few outliers), the correlation in each pair of metrics has small differences.

Fig. 4. Correlation coefficient between the user application related metric (frames displayed) and the four QoS related metrics.

To facilitate visualization further about the correlation between the four metrics and the QoE metric we illustrate in Fig.5 a representative session from UE #0, and from all samples collected during the 120 seconds of session #0. From this figure, we can notice a clear correlation between the QoE metric (Fig.5a) and averageCqiDl, rcvdSinrDl (Fig.5b-c) especially between the 45 and 70 seconds where the averageCqiDl, rcvdSinrDl are maximized and the percentage of framesdisplayed reaches 100%. Moreover, the end-to-end delay (Fig.5e) is minimized over this interval, designating also a high QoE offered to the end user. This analysis confirms the need to take into account the user-related characteristics when the QoE target metrics need to be estimated.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a novel architectural framework that ensures user-centric reliability by using various models and AI algorithms. Our vision is based on top of the open, heterogeneous and distributed 6G architecture, across the whole edge-cloud continuum. By collecting data from the monitoring probes placed in all possible layers of the ecosystem, we presented two profiling methods (service and security) in order to identify how the user-specific characteristics affect the QoE metrics and thus the reliability.

With the proposed profiling methods, the framework will be able to examine security threats and infrastructure-related issues that can affect service reliability and therefore propose some mitigation actions, such as scaling, resource allocation and migration. The presented evaluation and correlation analysis confirm the need to collect and include in future analyses unique user-related metrics when the QoE needs to be maximized.

VI. FUTURE WORK

In the future, we plan to develop and implement this user-centric reliability framework using various AI methods based on RL, DL, and FL. Multiple datasets, whether synthetic or not, will be investigated and collected across different administrative domains of the infrastructure, including data from the monitoring probes of all possible layers, such as the edge-cloud continuum, the 5G core system, and the application plane. The profiling methods will be tailored to the targets and objectives of each specific use case, ensuring the preservation of data privacy and security.

Fig. 5. Example of session #0 from UE #0 for five QoE (a) and QoS (b)-(e) metrics.

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